

THE INTEGRAL CONNECTION OF THE LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING "HAPPINESS" AND "UNHAPPINESS" IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE WITH THE NATIONAL WORLDVIEW.

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Abstract: This article shows the national-cultural characteristics of phraseological expressions related to the concepts of "Happiness" and "Unhappiness" in English and the translation of these phraseological units into Uzbek.

Key words: linguistic and cultural studies, concept, phraseological unit, paremiology.

As we explore cultural and historical changes in the concepts of happiness and unhappiness, first, we analyze the definitions of happiness and unhappiness in the dictionaries of 30 nations to understand cultural similarities and differences in the concepts of happiness and unhappiness. Second, we analyzed the definitions of happiness and unhappiness in Webster's dictionaries from 1850 to the present to understand historical changes in American English. Thirdly, we tried to study the State of the Union addresses given by US presidents from 1790 to 2010 within our topic. Finally, we looked at the appearance of happy and anti-happy expressions in Google Ngram Viewer from 1800 to 2008 to examine their usage. Concepts of happiness and unhappiness have always existed in different cultures and times, across time and space. We often use it to represent good luck and favorable external conditions, as well as unfortunate events and unpleasant events in life. However, in English this definition has been replaced by definitions focusing on favorable and unfavorable internal feeling states. Our research shows that the importance of the historical perspective in the study of psychological concepts emphasizes the differences in the meaning of each word in different times and places.

The concept of happiness is widely analyzed by philosophers and historians done Most philosophers and historians happiness in antiquity who agree that the concept is based on luck and fortune, whereas modern British happiness is controlled and active they see it as something they can aspire to. I am so happy for you. I know how much you wanted the job. In addition to expressing a feeling of pleasure, "happy" can often be used to describe people who are enjoying themselves. "Happy" is also used for a pleasant feeling of satisfaction, such as a feeling of contentment. In this sense, it is almost synonymous with "cheerful" and is used to express the good spirits and good qualities of a person who is happy about something or has an outgoing nature, and has a similar meaning. means names.

"Happy" combines with nouns denoting classes of people and even with "disposition", for example:

Marcia is a lovely girl with a happy / cheerful disposition.

"Unhappy" expresses the feeling of unhappiness, and this word can be connected with the character point of people in addition to its meaning. That is, we can use these types of words without any hesitation to express people of this nature. Among other things, we use this word to express the mood of dissatisfaction with life. We can also use words of this type to describe

closed, introverted people who are dissatisfied, sad, and dissatisfied with life by nature. For example:

John's unhappy mood today did not go unnoticed by around him.

The first meaning of the words "Happy" and "Unhappy" is widely used not only in everyday life, but also in literary works, and not only its scope of application has not lost its power long ago, but even now.

Causing or giving pleasure and contentment-zavq va mamnunlik sababidan yoki uni berish orqali yoki, Causing or giving anxiety and care-horg'inlik yoki g'am tuyg'ularining sababini ko'rsatish yoki ularni berish

The second meaning of the words "happiness" and "unhappiness" are used like the first meaning, and we refer to these words to describe an event, situation, or time when someone feels happy. Here "Happiness" also comes as a synonym of "blissful" quality. The adjective "blissfull" is used for an event, situation, or time when someone feels very happy and carefree. For example:

They are a young couple in the first blissful days of their marriage.

At this point, these words are used to express the periods of human life that are full of happiness and joy. For example:

Childhood- Happy Childhood.

She had very happy childhood memories.

Life- Blissfull life.

The times he knew as the brightest and blissfull moments of his life were as colorful as they are now.

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